

Effect of N source and insecticide treatment on ratoon crop. Siruguppa, India, 1985-86.

Treatment ^a	Regenerated tillers (no.)	Plant height (cm)	Tillers/plant	Panicles/plant	Sterility (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Harvest index
No N (control)	11	43.9	13	10	2.15	0.9	0.44
No N + monocrotophos	9	47.7	11	8	4.72	0.9	0.49
No N + chlorpyrifos	13	49.0	15	12	2.71	1.2	0.49
50 kg N/ha	22	63.9	20	21	2.11	2.2	0.44
50 kg N/ha + monocrotophos	22	64.3	26	20	1.25	1.9	0.41
50 kg N/ha + chlorpyrifos	18	60.0	24	17	0.93	1.9	0.44
Azolla	14	50.4	17	13	2.7	1.7	0.50
Azolla + monocrotophos	13	48.8	14	11	1.3	1.2	0.41
Azolla + chlorpyrifos	15	48.3	13	11	1.5	0.7	0.40
Azolla + 25 kg N/ha	18	56.6	21	17	1.3	2.0	0.52
Azolla + 25 kg N/ha + monocrotophos	21	53.3	24	14	1.8	1.5	0.45
Azolla + 25 kg N/ha + chlorpyrifos	23	56.8	20	18	1.2	1.4	0.45
CD (0.05)	4.26	7.80	0.98	9.4	0.52	0.74	0.09

^a Monocrotophos at 0.5 kg ai/ha, chlorpyrifos at 0.3 kg ai/ha, and azolla at 2.5 t/ha.

d after ratooning; plant height, tillers per plant, panicles per plant, sterility percentage, yield, and harvest index were noted at harvest (see table).

Number of regenerated tillers, panicles/plant, and yield varied considerably. In most treatments, some tillers regenerated after 15 d.

The interaction between N source and insecticide application had no significant effect on ratoon growth and development because there was no pest pressure on either the main or the ratoon crops. Fertilizer at 50 kg N/ha gave the highest mean ratoon yield. Applying azolla immediately after ratooning may not benefit the ratoon crop because azolla N is not available to the plant until the azolla decomposes. □

Effect of sesbania straw in a flooded soil on soil pH, redox potential, and water-soluble nutrients

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Information on release of nutrients other than N by green manures is scarce.

We studied the effect of Sesbania straw on Eh-pH kinetics and the release of water-soluble nutrients in a flooded rice soil in the laboratory.

The Crowley silt loam (Typic Albaqualf) collected from the Rice Experimental Station at Crowley, Louisiana, had pH 6.7, 0.81% organic C, and CEC 14.8 meq/100 g.

To monitor changes in Eh and pH, duplicate 60-g samples of air-dry soil, without or with 0.2% by weight sesbania

straw (2.5% N) were transferred into redox tubes. The tubes were constructed by sealing 12.5 mm of 18-gauge platinum wire on both sides of 40 × 138 mm pyrex test tubes, 25 mm from the bottom. The soil samples were submerged with an excess of deionized distilled water and incubated at 30 °C. pH and Eh measurements were made at intervals for 60 d.

To monitor release of water-soluble nutrients, duplicate 10-g portions of air-

1. Effect of sesbania straw on kinetics of pH and Eh in a flooded Crowley silt loam soil in the laboratory. Louisiana State University, 1987.

2. Effect of sesbania straw on water-soluble nutrients in a flooded Crowley silt loam soil in the laboratory. Louisiana State University, 1987.

dry soil, with and without sesbania straw, were transferred into 50-ml centrifuge tubes (25 × 100 ml) fitted with rubber septa. The soil samples were submerged with 25 ml of deionized distilled water. The tubes were weighed and incubated at 30°C. Moisture lost during incubation was replaced by weighing the tubes occasionally and adding water as needed.

At specified intervals, the tubes were shaken for 30 min, centrifuged at 7,000 rev/min for 20 min, and the solutions filtered through 0.45-µm filter paper. The samples were acidified to pH 2 with 12 N HCl and analyzed for different elements on an Inductive Coupled Argon Plasma emission spectrophotometer.

Decreases in soil Eh after flooding were more pronounced with the addition of sesbania straw (Fig. 1). At 60 d after flooding (DF), soil Eh decreased to -125 without sesbania and to -245 mV with sesbania. The Eh of the soil receiving sesbania stabilized at

30 DF, the Eh in unamended samples stabilized at 40 DF.

Increased soil reduction caused by incorporation of sesbania straw was also reflected by increases in soil pH. At 60 DF, soil pH increased from 6.8 to 7.2 without sesbania and to 7.4 with sesbania.

Incorporation of sesbania straw had a

variable effect on the release of water-soluble nutrients in the flooded soil (Fig. 2). Sesbania application caused marked increases of water-soluble Ca, Mg, P, Fe, and Mn. Those increases peaked 4 to 8 DF, then decreased. Sesbania straw had a slightly depressing effect on water-soluble Cu, Zn, and Al, but had no effect on water-soluble Si. □

Amelioration of highly alkali soil by karnal grass and para grass before rice - wheat cropping sequence

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To reclaim alkali soils (pH greater than 10), 12-15 t gypsum/ha followed by rice - wheat for 3-4 yr has been recommended. But gypsum is costly for small and marginal farmers.

We studied growing karnal grass [*Diplachne fusca* (Linn.) P. Beauv] and

para grass [*Brachiaria mutica* (Forsk.) Stapf.] as alternatives to gypsum.

The field was highly alkaline: pH 10.6 and exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) 94. Soil texture was sandy loam with 15% clay, 27% silt, and 58% sand. The experiment was conducted 1979-80 to 1983-84 in a split-plot design with four replications. The eight treatments are in the table.

Jaya rice and HD2009 wheat were sown throughout. Gypsum was applied 19 Jun 1979. Karnal grass and para grass were planted 8 Jul 1979.